

Impact of Digital Service Usage on the Human Resources Management Capacities of Vietnamese Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises

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Abstract

Background: There is a growing demand for small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) to utilise digital services to stay competitive in an era of rapid digital transformation. One of the areas most significantly impacted by digital tools is human resource management (HRM), as they have made it easier to recruit, train, and develop employees.

Objective: This study examines the impact of digital service usage on Vietnamese SMEs' HRM capabilities. It explores how leadership support, organisational readiness, policy procedures, perceived benefits, and company culture affect digital adoption and HRM development.

Methodology: Mixed methods were used. Interviews with 30 digital transformation specialists from five major cities refined measuring scales in the qualitative phase. Between July 2024 and February 2025, 1,000 SME managers in five provinces and five cities in Vietnam provided quantitative data. SEM was used to evaluate 11 hypotheses.

Result: Critically supporting all assumptions and digital service usage boosts HRM capacity and modulates other variables. Leadership supports best-predicted adoption and HRM results. Other elements, such as perceived benefits, policy procedures, and organisational preparation, also mattered.

Conclusion: Digital adoption plays a central role in enhancing HRM capacity in SMEs. Strategic leadership and supportive policy environments are critical factors for success.

Unique Contribution: This study presents an integrated framework that combines digital transformation and HRM theories, supported by novel empirical evidence from an emerging economy. Moreover, this is one of the studies to examine and assess the impact of digital services on improving HRM capacity in SMEs, providing a practical roadmap for digital HR transformation in developing nations.

Key Recommendation: Policymakers and SME leaders should prioritise digital leadership, infrastructure investment, and incentive policies to foster sustainable HRM development.

Keywords: Digital transformation, SMEs, HRM capacity, digital service adoption, Vietnam.

Introduction

The digital economy has fundamentally altered how organisations manage, communicate, and compete in the modern business landscape. In particular, adopting digital services has become a strategic imperative for enhancing efficiency, agility, and decision-making across core business functions. Among these, digital transformation has a profound influence on human resource management (Ulises & José, 2024). Organisations can better attract, develop, and retain talent while aligning workforce capabilities with strategic goals through digital tools such as human resource information systems, cloud-based talent platforms, and AI-enabled performance tracking systems.

In emerging economies such as Vietnam, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play a pivotal role in national economic development, accounting for a substantial portion of employment and making significant contributions to the GDP. However, many Vietnamese SMEs are still in the early stages of digital transformation. They face critical barriers, including limited financial and technical resources, underdeveloped infrastructure, fragmented policy support, and a shortage of digital skills among employees. Furthermore, there is often a lack of clear vision or leadership to guide the digitalisation of human resource practices. These challenges hinder their ability to adopt digital services and strengthen their HRM capacity effectively (Collings et al., 2021). Despite increasing global interest in digital HR transformation, the academic literature on digital service adoption in the context of Vietnamese SMEs, especially its impact on HRM capacity, remains limited. Most existing studies focus on large enterprises or developed economies, often overlooking the unique constraints and enablers of SMEs operating in transitional economies. Moreover, prior research has explored digital transformation or HRM in isolation, without integrating both domains within a unified analytical model (Venugopal et al., 2024; Abdalla et al., 2020).

This study develops and experimentally evaluates a conceptual model to investigate how digital service uptake impacts HRM capabilities in Vietnamese SMEs. The Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) model, Resource-Based View (RBV), and Institutional Theory are used to identify and assess internal and external factors affecting digital adoption. Leadership support, organisational preparation, policy procedures, perceived benefits, and culture (Nguar & Appolloni, 2024; Chen et al., 2024).

The study fills a critical research gap by investigating how digital service usage improves HRM capacity in Vietnamese SMEs. This area has been ignored in previous studies focusing on large corporations or developed countries. It combines HRM with digital transformation theories, providing empirical insights through a mixed-methods approach in an emerging economy

setting.

The research employs mixed methods, incorporating in-depth interviews with 30 digital transformation specialists from five major cities to enrich context-relevant measurement scales in the qualitative phase. After collecting data from 1,000 SME managers in 10 provinces and cities from July 2024 to February 2025, structural equation modelling is used for rigorous statistical analysis. This study is significant because it addresses the underexplored intersection of digital transformation and human resource management in small and medium-sized enterprises in emerging markets. Based on research into Vietnamese SMEs, new insights are gained into how digital adoption enhances HRM capacity, thereby improving both academic understanding and policymaking for long-term economic and workforce development. Therefore, the objective of this paper is to examine how digital service uptake affects HRM capability in Vietnamese SMEs and give practical advice for SMEs and policymakers navigating digital HRM in Vietnam.

Literature Review

Human Resource Management Capacity (HRMC)

An organisation's capacity to strategically and efficiently manage its human resources is known as human resource management. It is part of the process of recruiting, developing, training, managing performance, engaging employees, and retaining talent. Human resource management competence in the digital era also involves leveraging data and technology to inform better decisions (Venugopal et al., 2024). High HRM capability enables a company to respond to change, grow sustainably, and align HR with business strategy. To successfully navigate digital change, SMEs must enhance their HRM capacity. As a performance facilitator, it impacts creativity, productivity, and the organisation's long-term success.

Adoption of Digital Services (ADS)

When small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) adopt digital services, they use and incorporate digital technology into their operations. This category encompasses resources such as HR information systems, online learning management systems, performance dashboards, digital recruitment platforms, and cloud computing solutions. Technology must be actively utilised to enhance business processes and decision-making for it to be considered adopted (Abdalla et al., 2020). Factors in the technical, organisational, and environmental domains all contribute to the widespread use of the TOE framework. To mediate the relationship between HRM inputs and outputs in terms of capacity, digital service adoption facilitates strategic workforce planning, boosts operational efficiency, and raises employee engagement.

Perceived Benefits (PE)

Managers' and employees' perceptions of the value of digital service adoption to the company. This may involve improving efficiency, achieving cost savings, enhancing decision-making, increasing customer satisfaction, or enhancing employee performance (Nguar & Appolloni, 2024). According to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), perceived utility is a strong predictor of technology adoption. When SMEs see how digital transformation can enhance HRM processes, such as recruitment, training, and performance management, they are more likely to implement technology and invest in HR development. Thus, perceived rewards influence intention and action.

Organisational Culture (OC)

Organisational culture is the shared values, beliefs, norms, and practices that shape employee behaviour. It affects how employees adapt, innovate, and collaborate. A culture that values learning, adaptation, and the adoption of technology is more likely to utilise digital services (Bagga et al., 2022). The Resource-Based View (RBV) considers culture a strategic intangible asset that can either enhance or hinder capability development. In SMEs with strong informal norms, culture has a significant impact on digital transformation and HR system evolution.

Policy Mechanisms (PM)

Policy mechanisms assist or regulate the digital transformation of businesses through government or institutional initiatives. Examples include financial incentives, digital infrastructure, regulatory frameworks, training, and national innovation plans (Jani et al., 2021). Policy strategies lower technology costs, bridge competence gaps, and encourage SME digital economy involvement in emerging nations. The institutional theory says enterprises respond to policy incentives and pressures. Policy measures help Vietnamese SMEs utilise digital tools and enhance their human resource management systems to achieve digital goals.

Organisational Readiness (ORR)

Internal infrastructure, digital skills, financial resources, and procedural flexibility determine an organisation's technological readiness. A "ready" company has the technology, skills, and management to adopt and sustain digital advancements (Chen et al., 2024). The Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) concept predicts technology adoption based on organisational readiness. SME preparedness includes technical, strategic, and innovative attitudes. Digital transformation and HR operational agility improve with readiness.

Leadership Support (LS)

Leadership support refers to the extent to which senior management promotes, facilitates, and invests in digital transformation and strategic HR development. It involves creating goals, allocating resources, and encouraging staff innovation (Dirani et al., 2020). Leadership assistance is crucial in SMEs due to centralised decision-making and limited resources. Supportive leadership reduces resistance to change and enhances organisational readiness. Employee motivation is vital for digital initiatives and HR capacity development. TOE and RBV frameworks see leadership support as a critical enabler of organisational transformation.

Theoretical Framework

Leadership Support (LS), Adoption of Digital Services (ADS), Human Resource Management Capacity (HRMC)

Organisational functions, including HR management, are strategically guided by leadership support. Leaders who actively support HR and digital transformation are more likely to invest in HR capacity, innovation, and workforce strategies that align with technological development (Ulises & José, 2024). Leadership vision and devotion may overcome structural constraints in SMEs. Leadership involvement enhances HRM outcomes by empowering employees to develop their capabilities and learn within institutions (Dirani et al., 2020). Also, leadership is

crucial to digital transformation. Top management attitudes and decisions have a significant impact on the adoption of digital services in SMEs. Supportive leadership reduces change resistance, optimises resource allocation, and fosters innovation (Ulrich et al., 2024). The technology-organisation-environment framework and the UTAUT model suggest that top management support drives digital adoption (Beletskiy & Fey, 2021). Digital leaders enhance workforce confidence and organisational readiness for technology adoption. Therefore, the authors proposed H1 and H2 in Figure 1.

Organisational Readiness (ORR), Adoption of Digital Services (ADS), Human Resource Management Capacity (HRMC)

Organisational readiness refers to a company's technological infrastructure, the capabilities of its people, and its internal processes for adopting digital technology. Digitally ready companies are agile, can integrate new systems, and adapt to change. The TOE framework emphasises organisational preparedness as a key driver of technology adoption. SMEs may be ready with skilled IT staff, training plans, or adaptable operational processes (Fiaz & Qureshi, 2024). Even useful technology is unlikely to be adopted efficiently without readiness. HRM capacity is also directly affected by a firm's digital infrastructure and organisational flexibility. Companies can better deliver modern HR processes, such as digital recruitment, training, and performance tracking, with the right technology and resources (Chen et al., 2024). Organisational readiness aligns HR and business goals, particularly in digitally evolving environments, fosters HR innovation, and enhances employee satisfaction. Therefore, the authors proposed H3 and H4 in Figure 1.

Policy Mechanisms (PM), Adoption of Digital Services (ADS), Human Resource Management Capacity (HRMC)

Government support programs, tax incentives, and digital transformation roadmaps encourage technology adoption, particularly among SMEs. Public policy may lower risks and boost digital investment. Institutional theory says regulatory and normative influences shape organisational behaviour (Thite, 2022). The policy compensates for limited internal resources and promotes digital involvement in emerging markets. Strong policy frameworks encourage small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to utilise digital services to enhance their competitiveness (Zhang & Chen, 2023). In many developing economies, including Vietnam, digital transformation policies have an indirect impact on human resource development. The government can help SMEs create digital HR capabilities by offering training subsidies, technology grants, or regulatory guidelines. Policy tools lower digital tool entrance barriers and support enterprise personnel upskilling. Research indicates that effective policies enhance capacity, particularly in Human Resource Management (HRM). Therefore, the authors proposed H5 and H6 in Figure 1.

Organisational Culture (OC), Adoption of Digital Services (ADS), Human Resource Management Capacity (HRMC)

Corporate culture influences employee attitudes toward change, learning, and innovation. A culture that values innovation, open communication, and digital literacy encourages technology adoption. Adaptability and engagement are cultural attributes that promote technological change (Bukoye & Abdulrahman, 2022). SMEs' flatter hierarchies make cultural alignment

even more critical. Restrictive cultures may resist digital technologies, but proactive cultures facilitate their adoption. A company's culture also affects its digital orientation, development, and maintenance of HRM. Learning, collaboration, and innovation-focused cultures foster human capital (Bagga et al., 2022). The resource-based view (RBV) posits that intangible assets, such as culture, shape organisational competencies, particularly in human resource management (HRM). Therefore, the authors proposed H7 and H8 in Figure 1.

Perceived Benefits (PE), Adoption of Digital Services (ADS), Human Resource Management Capacity (HRMC)

The extent to which decision-makers believe digital technology will benefit the firm is referred to as perceived benefits. According to the Technology Acceptance Model, perceived utility drives technology adoption (Autsadee et al., 2023). Managers are more likely to use digital services if they believe these services improve efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance HR outcomes. A critical antecedent is that SMEs with limited finances assess perceived benefits more critically than large enterprises (Ekuma, 2023). Beyond digital adoption, anticipated benefits influence how organisations perceive and invest in HRM capabilities. When SMEs believe digital technologies will improve talent management, employee performance, and HR processes, they invest more in HR development. Positive attitudes promote proactive modernisation. According to research, HR investment is driven by perceived strategic value, as proposed in H9 and H10 in Figure 1.

Adoption of Digital Services (ADS) and Human Resource Management Capacity (HRMC)

Digital services provide automation, better decision-making, and data-driven HR initiatives. E-learning, performance dashboards, staff engagement, and online recruitment are made possible by digital tools. Thus, organisations using such tools can better manage their workers (Charlwood & Guenole, 2022). SEM studies in emerging markets show that digital adoption improves HRM capabilities. Thus, the authors proposed Hypothesis H11 (Figure 1).

The authors chose to inherit five factors influencing the adoption of digital service and human resource management capacity at SMEs in Vietnam. Specifically, the research model is as follows in Figure 1:

Source: The authors proposed the model

Figure 1: Impacting the adoption of digital service on human resource management capacity

Figure 1 illustrates five critical factors of career competency that impact employees' job performance in commercial banks in Vietnam. These essential factors, including leadership support, organisational readiness, policy mechanisms, perceived benefits, and organisational culture, serve as determinants of digital adoption and HRM capacity.

Research Methods

This study adopts a mixed-method approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative research methods to ensure theoretical robustness and empirical validity. The mixed-method design was implemented in two main phases: (1) qualitative exploration and (2) quantitative validation.

Qualitative phase: The qualitative phase aims to explore practical insights from industry experts and refine measurement items for each construct in the proposed model. Moreover, a total of 30 experts in digital transformation were selected using purposive sampling. All participants had at least five years of professional experience managing or consulting on SMEs' digital transformation projects. Experts were drawn from five major cities in Vietnam, including Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Da Nang, Hai Phong, and Can Tho. Semi-structured interviews and expert panel discussions focused on (1) Key factors influencing digital service adoption. (2) Challenges in HRM capacity development. (3) Perceived value of policy, culture, and leadership in digital contexts. (4) The qualitative data were analysed using thematic coding supported by NVivo software. Key dimensions and patterns were identified and mapped to existing theoretical constructs. Insights were used to develop or revise measurement items for the formal survey instrument. (5) The qualitative phase yields a validated set of scale items, serving as the foundation for the quantitative survey instrument. These scales reflect academic theory and local context (Hair et al., 2018).

Quantitative phase: The quantitative phase empirically tests the proposed SEM model through

survey data. The process followed five structured steps.

Step 1: Instrument Development - The quantitative phase began with the development of a structured survey instrument. Scale items were adapted from existing validated sources grounded in theories such as the Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) framework, the Resource-Based View (RBV), and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Items were further refined through insights gathered during the qualitative phase with 30 digital transformation experts. The included questionnaire consisted of 11 constructs, each with five items, using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). A pilot test was conducted with 20 SME managers to ensure the clarity, relevance, and linguistic appropriateness of the items. Feedback from the pilot was used to refine clear items and ensure cultural alignment with the Vietnamese SME context. This step lays the groundwork for robust measurement in the later stages.

Step 2: Sampling and data collection - The survey was administered to a target sample of 1.000 SME managers across five major cities (Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Da Nang, Hai Phong, Can Tho) and five leading provinces (Bac Ninh, Binh Duong, Dong Nai, Quang Ninh, Thua Thien Hue) between July 2024 and February 2025. The sampling strategy employs a combination of stratified and convenience sampling, ensuring geographic diversity and cross-sectoral representation (e.g., manufacturing, trade, IT services, logistics). Respondents included CEOs, HR managers, and digital transformation executives with in-depth knowledge of their firms' digital practices and HR operations. Surveys were distributed online and on paper via SME support centres and professional networks. A research team based in each region assisted in local data collection and verification. This step aims to collect a sufficient dataset for structural equation modelling (Hair et al., 2018).

Step 3: Preliminary data screening - After the data was collected, a thorough screening of the 1.000 returned surveys was carried out. It all started with removing answers with too much missing or inconsistent data. The skewness and kurtosis were then evaluated using normality tests. Using the Mahalanobis distance, we identified multivariate outliers. To ensure that no single component explained most of the variation, we used Harman's single-factor test to assess standard method bias. We also double-checked the demographic and firmographic profiles to ensure they aligned with our target audience. After filtering, responses that met the criteria for high quality were kept for further study. This step aimed to verify that the data were valid, consistent, and suitable for structural modelling, following data cleaning and preparation. SPSS 20.0 and Excel were utilised (Hair et al., 2018).

Step 4: Measurement model evaluation (CFA) - To ensure the reliability and validity of the measurement scales, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted using AMOS 20.0. Reliability, convergent, and discriminant validity were the three characteristics used to evaluate the model's measurement properties. Both Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR) were used to measure reliability, and it was anticipated that both would exceed 0.70. An Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value greater than 0.50 was used to confirm convergent validity. The Fornell-Larcker criterion was used to evaluate discriminant validity. Each item's factor loading had to be more than 0.60. To assess the model's fit, goodness-of-fit indices were utilised, including CFI > 0.90, TLI > 0.90, RMSEA < 0.08, and SRMR < 0.08. The CFA results are necessary to proceed with structural model analysis (Hair et al., 2018).

Step 5: Structural Equation Model Testing (SEM) - The final stage employed structural equation modelling (SEM) to examine the eleven hypotheses and assess the correlations between the variables. The path coefficients, t-values, and significance levels of the structural

model were estimated using Amos 20.0. We employed bootstrapping approaches to assess the mediating effect of digital service adoption. To better understand how leadership, preparedness, culture, policy, and perceived advantages affect HRM capacity, we examined direct, indirect, and total effects. To confirm the model's structure, goodness-of-fit indices were reevaluated. This study provided empirical evidence to support theory-driven discoveries and to elucidate the relative strengths and importance of each pathway. Practical and theoretical implications regarding digital transformation in SMEs were drawn from the findings of this stage.

Results

Testing key factors affecting the adoption of digital service and human resource management capacity at SMEs in Vietnam

Table 1: Testing of Cronbach's alpha for factors affecting the adoption of digital service and human resource management capacity

Items	Cronbach's alpha	Mean	Std. Deviation
Leadership support (LS)	0.932	3.024	1.005
Organisational readiness (ORR)	0.944	3.049	0.973
Policy mechanisms (PM)	0.941	3.054	1.003
Organisational culture (OC)	0.926	2.497	0.803
Perceived benefits (PE)	0.860	3.408	0.939
Adoption of digital services (ADS)	0.891	3.307	0.984
Human resource management capacity (HRMC)	0.834	2.370	0.656

Source: own calculations in SPSS 20.0.

Table 1 presents the internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's Alpha) and descriptive statistics for seven key constructs. All factors exhibit high reliability, with Cronbach's Alpha values exceeding 0.83, indicating strong internal consistency across the items. The constructs organisational readiness (0.944) and policy mechanisms (0.941) show the highest reliability, followed by leadership support (0.932) and organisational culture (0.926). These findings provide a strong foundation for further analysis, such as exploratory factor analysis and structural equation modelling.

Table 2: Testing the SEM model for factors affecting the adoption of digital service and human resource management capacity

Relationships	Standardized Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	SE-Bias	Hypothesis	Result
LS → ADS	0.575	0.029	17.287	***	0.001	H2	Accepted
ORR → ADS	0.060	0.026	2.122	0.034	0.003	H4	Accepted
PM → ADS	0.100	0.022	3.578	***	0.004	H5	Accepted
OC → ADS	0.068	0.033	2.693	0.007	0.005	H7	Accepted
PE → ADS	0.141	0.030	4.667	***	0.003	H9	Accepted

Relationships			Standardized Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	SE-Bias	Hypothesis	Result
LS	→	HRMC	0.325	0.022	8.159	***	0.001	H1	Accepted
ORR	→	HRMC	0.107	0.018	3.543	***	0.004	H3	Accepted
PM	→	HRMC	0.066	0.015	2.286	0.022	0.001	H6	Accepted
OC	→	HRMC	0.098	0.022	3.610	***	0.003	H8	Accepted
PE	→	HRMC	0.085	0.020	2.700	0.007	0.001	H10	Accepted
ADS	→	HRMC	0.332	0.026	8.033	***	0.001	H11	Accepted

*Source: Authors collected and processed from SPSS 20.0, Amos, Note *** significance at 0.01.*

Table 2 presents the results assessing the influence of organisational factors on the adoption of digital services (ADS) and human resource management capacity (HRMC). All predicted paths (H1–H11) are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating strong empirical support for the proposed model. Among the predictors of ADS, leadership support (LS) has the most significant impact ($\beta = 0.575$), followed by perceived benefits (PE) ($\beta = 0.141$) and policy mechanisms (PM) ($\beta = 0.100$). Organisational readiness (ORR) and organisational culture (OC) have more minor yet significant influences. Regarding HRMC, ADS ($\beta = 0.332$) and LS ($\beta = 0.325$) exert the most potent effects. Other contributors include ORR, PM, OC, and PE, although their effects are more modest. These results confirm that leadership and digital technologies directly enhance HR capabilities, while structural and cultural conditions enable the adoption of these factors. Overall, the SEM confirms the validity of all hypotheses, highlighting the interconnected roles of leadership, policy, readiness, and perceived value in digital transformation success.

Source: Authors collected and processed from SPSS 20.0, Amos

Figure 3: Testing SEM for factors affecting the adoption of digital service and human resource management capacity

Figure 3 illustrates the significance threshold of 0.05 for evaluating five key components of adopting digital service and human resource management capabilities in small and medium-sized enterprises in Vietnam. The following statistical metrics measured the model's fit: GFI = 0.925 (>0.900), TLI = 0.953 (>0.900), CFI = 0.962 (> 0.900), and RMSEA = 0.056 (< 0.1) in Figure 3. According to the data presented above, research model testing revealed five critical factors affecting digital service adoption and human resource management capacity, with a significance level of 0.05. Figure 3 validates the comprehensive framework that links strategic, structural, and perceptual elements to successful digital transformation and the enhancement of HR capacity.

Discussion of findings

All factors in the model are significant and positively influence the adoption of digital services and HR capacity. Leadership support and adoption of digital services are the most impactful core enablers of digital transformation. Factors like perceived benefits, readiness, and culture are foundational supports that indirectly strengthen HR development through digital adoption.

Leadership support is crucial for digital service uptake ($\beta = 0.575$) and for building human resource management capacity ($\beta = 0.325$). Leaders who actively encourage digital transformation through clear vision, direction, and effective resource allocation strengthen their company's readiness and foster employee buy-in. Leadership fosters a strategic environment that promotes innovation, talent development, and effective performance management, thereby enhancing HR capacity. Clear direction and inspiration from practical leadership help overcome resistance to change. Strong top-level support is essential for digital projects and long-term human capital expansion.

Despite the mild effects, organisational readiness has a significant impact on digital adoption ($\beta = 0.060$) and HR capacity ($\beta = 0.107$). This element demonstrates an organisation's digital expertise, technology infrastructure, and readiness for change. A well-prepared company reduces staff resistance to digital implementation. Its significant impact on HRMC implies that preparedness is essential for system utilisation and people-driven transformation. Infrastructure, digital literacy, and adaptive planning are necessary to foster both technological and human growth.

Policy mechanisms have a positive impact on digital service adoption ($\beta = 0.100$) and HR capacity ($\beta = 0.066$), underscoring the importance of structured frameworks. Policy clarity, support, and alignment with digital goals influence employee behaviour and improve execution. Clear regulations, digital guidelines, incentive programs, and compliance frameworks foster transformation. HR policies that encourage upskilling, digital onboarding, and performance measures boost effectiveness. Effective policy stabilises digital transition and ensures institutional expectations and operational efficiency, notwithstanding its small influence.

Organisational culture influences digital adoption ($\beta = 0.068$) and HR capability ($\beta = 0.098$), highlighting the importance of shared values and innovation awareness. Digital change requires collaboration, risk-taking, and adaptation, which supportive cultures enable. It reduces change resistance by getting people to use new tools and processes. Positive HR management cultures encourage learning, accountability, and shared goals. Culture guides technological perception and use. Strengthening an innovation-driven culture supports technical, social, and behavioural acceptance of digital solutions.

Benefit perception has a substantial impact on digital adoption ($\beta = 0.141$) and HR capacity ($\beta = 0.085$). Employees are more likely to support the adoption of digital services if they improve efficiency, reduce workload, or yield better outcomes (Fiaz & Qureshi, 2024; Charlwood & Guenole, 2022; Autsadee et al., 2023). Usefulness changes behaviour and boosts commitment. Digital technologies for performance tracking and development aid HRM capacity-building. Success stories, user feedback, and training all boost confidence and encourage involvement in digital transformation.

Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

Conclusions

This study investigates the impact of digital service adoption on human resource management capacity among small and medium enterprises in Vietnam. Based on an integrated model

grounded in the Technology-Organization-Environment framework, Resource-Based View, and institutional theory, the study examines how internal and external factors influence digital adoption and HRM capacity. The results of the structural equation modelling, based on a sample of 1,000 SME managers across five provinces and five cities in Vietnam, confirmed that digital service adoption plays a critical mediating role in enhancing HRM capacity. Leadership Support emerged as the most influential factor among the antecedents, positively impacting ADS and HRMC. Perceived benefits, policy mechanisms, organisational culture, and organisational readiness were also found to influence ADS, although at varying intensity levels significantly. Furthermore, all five contextual factors directly affected HRMC, with ADS contributing the highest total effect. These findings provide robust empirical evidence that a successful digital transformation strategy must consider economic and human elements, particularly in resource-constrained SME environments.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings, several policy and management implications can be proposed to support digital HR transformation in SMEs: (1) Strengthen digital leadership in SMEs - Government programs should support the development of digital leadership skills through training and mentoring for SME owners and managers. This will empower them to lead digital initiatives with vision and commitment. (2) Enhance digital readiness infrastructure - Policymakers should expand digital infrastructure investments, particularly in non-urban areas. SMEs require accessible platforms and affordable technologies to initiate their digital transformation. (3) Develop tailored policy mechanisms - Incentive programs such as tax reductions, digital adoption grants, and e-HRM pilot projects should be introduced specifically for SMEs. A dedicated support mechanism for digital HR tools can fast-track HRM capacity building. (4) Promote digital organisational culture - Programs encouraging knowledge sharing, innovation, and openness to technology should be embedded in SME support ecosystems. Chambers of commerce and industry associations can play a role in disseminating best practices. (5) Raise awareness of digital value - National communication campaigns and workshops should emphasise the tangible benefits of digital transformation, particularly in HRM, helping SMEs perceive it as an investment rather than a cost.

Limitations and future research: This study has several limitations. First, its cross-sectional design restricts the ability to draw causal inferences. Second, data were self-reported by SME managers, which may introduce bias. Third, the study focused on selected cities and provinces, which may limit generalizability. Future research should adopt longitudinal approaches to track changes over time and explore sector-specific or regional variations. Comparative studies across different countries or industries may offer broader insights. Additionally, multi-level analyses and qualitative follow-ups could provide a deeper understanding of organisational behaviour and digital adoption dynamics in HRM transformation.

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